

Spectrophotometric study of adduct of nickel(II) di(2-bromo-4-methylphenyl)carbazone with nitrogen bases

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Abstract : The stability constants of the adducts formed between square planar nickel(II) chelate of di(2-bromo-4-methylphenyl)carbazone with nitrogen bases are obtained from spectrophotometric measurements in chloroform solution at room temperature. The monodentate bases form hexacoordinated adducts with 1 : 2 stoichiometry for metal chelate-base. Saturated nitrogen bases form pentacoordinated adducts. Variations in their stability of these adducts with the bases are attributed to changes in their donor power. Stability of these adducts are discussed in terms of steric hindrance, basicity and ring structure.

Keywords : Stability constant, nitrogen bases, adduct.

The reaction of different Lewis bases with 4-coordinate nickel(II) chelates of the type NiS_2^1 , NiS_2O_2^2 and NiS_2N_2^3 have been investigated extensively. Much less data, however, have been reported for the reaction of NiN_2O_2^4 chelates with such bases. A series of NiN_2O_2 chelates with monodentate and bidentate ligands derived from substituted diphenylcarbazones have been prepared and characterised^{3,5}. These chelates are found to react with pyridines and anilines forming either pentacoordinate mono adducts or hexacoordinate bis adducts depending on the nature of substituents in nickel(II) chelates.

In the present work, we have further investigated the interaction of nickel(II) chelate of di(2-bromo-4-methylphenyl)carbazone, $\text{Ni}(\text{2B4MPC})_2$, with some nitrogen bases to gain quantitative information about the nature and the stability of the adduct formed. The nitrogen bases selected in this study were pyridine, substituted pyridines, aniline, methyl, chloro and bromo substituted anilines. All the reactions were carried out in chloroform as a solvent which does not added axially to the planar nickel(II) chelate.

Results and discussion

Chloroform solutions of $\text{Ni}(\text{2B4MPC})_2$ are intense blue coloured with an absorption band at 570 nm ($\epsilon_{570} = 4.0$

$\times 10^4 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and a shoulder at around 630 nm ($\epsilon_{639} = 3.5 \times 10^4 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in contrast to most of the other metal-2B4MPC complexes, those of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} have a single absorption band at about 550 nm. The spectrum of $\text{Ni}(\text{2B4MPC})_2$ undergoes a profound change on addition of certain nitrogen bases, giving a single absorption band around 530 nm. There are two isosbestic points in the visible region for $\text{Ni}(\text{2B4MPC})_2$ adduct system, at around 540 and 420 nm.

The change in the spectra of nickel(II) chelate on addition of nitrogen bases could be used to determine stability constants of the adducts formed. The absorption values at 630 nm were plotted as a function of pB to obtain sigmoidal curves. The values of A_{ad} were obtained from the extrapolation of curves which are used in the calculation of overall formation constants β_n^{ad} of the adducts using eq. (1) :

$$\log \beta_n^{\text{ad}} = -n \log [B] + \log (A_{\text{ch}} - A)/(A - A_{\text{ad}}) \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of base, B , molecules attached to the chelate; A_{ch} and A_{ad} are respectively the absorbances due to chelates and adducts and A is the absorbance due to chelate adduct equilibrium mixture. The stoichiometry of adducts formed due to the reaction of Ni^{II} chelate with nitrogen bases were established by mole-ratio and Job's methods.

For the adducts of $\text{Ni}(\text{2B4MPC})_2$ with aniline bases, the approximate $\log \beta_n^{\text{ad}}$ values increase linearly with $\text{p}K_a$ for the conjugate acid of the base. These adducts contain two moles of base as shown by the slope of 2 for the plots of $\log (A_{\text{ch}} - A)/(A - A_{\text{ad}})$ vs $-\log [B]$. This accounts for six coordination sites around nickel. The experimental results are given in Table 1.

In case of adduct formation of $\text{Ni}(\text{2B4MPC})_2$ with quinoline, it has been found that the adduct contain one mole of base as shown by the slope of 1. This accounts for the formation of pentacoordinated adduct with 1 : 1 stoichiometry for metal chelate-quinoline.

The stabilities of nickel(II) adducts were found to increase in the following order of bases : 2-chloroaniline \sim 2-bromoaniline \sim 2,4-dichloroaniline < 2-methylaniline < 4-chloroaniline < aniline < 4-acetylpyridine < quinoline < 4-bromoaniline < 4-methylpyridine < 2-aminopyridine < pyridine < 2-amino-4-methylpyridine. The lower stabilities of 2-me-

thyl, 2-bromo, 2-chloroaniline and 2-aminopyridine compared to aniline and pyridine respectively, may be attributed to the steric hindrance offered by methyl, bromo, chloro and amino groups present at 2-position, even though their $\text{p}K_a$ values are much higher than aniline. The stability constants of methyl anilines were found to be higher than chloro and bromoanilines. Stability constant strongly depends on the electron withdrawing or donating characteristics of the substituents in a series of substituted anilines and pyridines⁶. The stability of 4-methylaniline adduct relative to that 4-chloroaniline adduct reflect the increased donor power of the nitrogen atom due to substituent effect. The same trend is noticed also with 2-amino-4-methylpyridine compared with 4-acetylpyridine. It is however interesting to note that bromoanilines form strong adducts than chloroanilines. It is because bromo is less electron withdrawing characteristic than chloro substituents.

Pentacoordinated adducts were obtained with saturated heterocyclic bases with 1 : 1 stoichiometry. The smaller formation constants of the adduct of $\text{Ni}(\text{2B4MPC})_2$ with morpholine may be attributed due to decreased basicity of nitrogen atom in the morpholine ring.

From the study of adduct formation of nickel(II) chelate with saturated heterocyclic nitrogen bases, it is clear that the structural and electrostatic rearrangements in the donor as well as in the acceptor molecules must be considered in the interpretation of adduct formation. With strong nitrogen bases a considerable distortion takes place in the formation of nickel(II) chelate adducts. The donor molecules themselves must undergo structural changes⁷.

Polar solvents like DMF, 1,4-dioxan and ethanol also form adducts like nitrogen bases. Ethyl alcohol forms most stable adduct with $\text{Ni}(\text{2B4MPC})_2$ than DMF and 1,4-dioxan.

The absorption spectrum of $\text{Ni}(\text{2B4MPC})_2$ does not change upon the addition of 2-methyl-8-quinolinol, 4-methyl-8-quinolinol, 2-nitroaniline, 3-nitroaniline and 4-nitroaniline. This may be due to the fact that these ligands do not form adducts with $\text{Ni}(\text{2B4MPC})_2$ under these experimental conditions.

It is interesting to note that the adduct formation constants for $\text{Ni}(\text{2B4MPC})_2$ are significantly higher than its sulphur and nitrogen nickel(II) chelates³, indicating that the adducts of nickel(II) chelates with O and N atoms prefer higher coordination number than four.

Experimental

The reagent di(2-bromo-4-methylphenyl)carbazone was

Table 1. Adduct formation constants of $\text{Ni}(\text{2B4MPC})_2$ in chloroform

Base	$\text{p}K_a$	Slope (n)	$\log \beta_n^{\text{ad}}$
Aniline	4.63 ^a	2	1.98
2-Methylaniline	4.44 ^a	2	1.00
4-Methylaniline	5.08 ^a	2	2.35
2-Chloroaniline	2.65 ^a	2	0.56
4-Chloroaniline	4.15 ^a	2	1.04
2-Bromoaniline		2	0.84
4-Bromoaniline	3.86 ^a	2	2.20
2,4-Dichloroaniline		2	0.96
Pyridine	5.20 ^a	2	4.12
2-Chloropyridine		NAF*	-
2-Aminopyridine	6.82 ^b	2	3.80
2-Amino-4-methylpyridine		2	4.59
4-Acetylpyridine		2	2.02
Piperidine	11.12 ^a	1	2.06
Morpholine	8.33 ^a	1	2.98
Quinoline	4.90 ^a	1	1.98
2-Methyl-8-quinolinol		NAF*	
4-Methyl-8-quinolinol		NAF*	
2-Nitroaniline	-0.29 ^b	NAF*	
3-Nitroaniline	2.47 ^b	NAF*	
Ethyl alcohol		2	0.90
Dimethylformamide		2	0.18
1,4-Dioxan		2	0.06

*NAF : No Adduct Formation.

^aRef. 11, ^bRef. 12.

prepared by the persulphate oxidation of the corresponding carbazide as reported in the literature⁸. The product was purified by passing its ethereal solution through the silica gel column using dry ether as eluent to obtain pure sample (m.p. 135 °C). Pyridine (Fisher), 4-acetylpyridine, morpholine, piperidine, quinoline, aniline, 2-methyl, 3-methyl, 2-chloro, 4-chloroanilines and 2-bromoaniline were dried over KOH and constant boiling fractions collected and used. 4-Methylaniline, 4-bromoaniline, 2,4-dichloroaniline, 2-aminopyridine, 2-amino-4-methylpyridine, nitroanilines and 8-quinolinol (B.D.H.) were used as such without further purification. Chloroform, 1,4-dioxan, dimethylformamide (B.D.H.) and ethyl alcohol were purified by the method suggested by Vogel⁹.

A Bausch and Lomb Spectronic 2000 UV-visible recording spectrophotometer and Systronic spectrophotometer 106 were used for absorbance measurements.

Preparation of Ni(2B4MPC)₂ complex : Approximately 1 g of nickel(II) chloride (Fisher, AnalaR) was dissolved in an acetate buffer of pH = 6.20 and mixed with an appropriate amount of di(2-bromo-4-methylphenyl)-carbazone in ethanolic solution. The mixture was stirred and the precipitate formed was washed several times with water. The complex was dried at room temperature over phosphorus pentoxide under vacuum. It was then purified by Soxhlet method⁹ using dry ether to get pure com-

plex (m.p. 220–221 °C). The nickel content of the complex was found to be 6.42% by the phenanthroline-dithizone method¹⁰.

The absorbance value of the chelate and the adduct differ maximum at 630 nm (which is stable for 1 h) and all measurements were carried out at this wavelength. A typical spectra of Ni(2B4MPC)₂-pyridine adduct system is shown in Fig. 1. The absorbance values were also used to obtain mole-ratio and Job's plot³.

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Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of (Ni2B4MPC)₂ + pyridine mixtures in chloroform at 25 °C. [Ni(2B4MPC)₂] : 2.1 × 10⁻⁵ M. [pyridine], × 10⁻⁵ M : (a) 0.00, (b) 0.30, (c) 1.45, (d) 2.90, (e) 5.80, (f) 8.70, (g) 11.61, (h) 14.51, (i) 17.42, (j) 20.32, (k) 23.22, (l) 29.03, (m) 58.06, (n) 64.00.